

Seismic Response Reduction by Multiple TMDs for Cylindrical Lattice Arch Roof Supported by Single Story Substructure Simulating School Gymnasium on Scaled Shaking Table Test

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Abstract

In this research, shaking table tests have been conducted on 1/4-scale school gymnasium frame with cylindrical lattice arch roof supported by single-story substructures with tuned mass dampers (TMDs) at E-Defense. TMD is one of the vibration control devices that can be applied to spatial structures. TMD has the advantage that the vibration control effect can be obtained by the mass of 1 to 3% of structure. In addition, TMD is fit for the vibration control of spatial structures because it is possible to install TMDs by single supporting point. The purpose of this study is to investigate the seismic response reduction effects by installing on roof dual TMDs designed based on optimal condition formulae on scaled shaking table tests. Finally, the correspondence between the results by the experiments and the results by the reproduced analyses are examined.

Keywords: Cylindrical lattice arch roof, Single story substructure, Shaking table test, Gable directional input, multiple TMDs, Seismic response reduction effect.

1. Introduction

TMD is one of the vibration control devices that can be applied to spatial structures. TMD has the advantage that the vibration control effect can be obtained by the mass of 1 to 3% of structure. In addition, TMD is fit for the vibration control of spatial structures because it is possible to install TMDs by single supporting point. Therefore, there are many studies by numerical analyses dealing with the vibration control of spatial structures by installing multiple TMDs. However, experimental studies have been conducted only in the arch model, and there have been no experiments to examine the seismic response reduction by multiple TMDs of arch roof supported by single story substructure using more realistic frame. The purpose of this study is to investigate the seismic response reduction effects by installing on roof dual TMDs designed based on optimal condition formulae (Iwanami and Seto [1], Kamiya et al. [2]) for the 1/4-scale model of the cylindrical lattice arch roof by single story substructure on scaled shaking table tests. This paper begins with preliminary analysis of the multiple TMDs design, analysis of TMDs performance test results and the basic information of the test setups installing on roof dual TMDs. The design values of TMDs are determined after obtaining the natural vibration characteristics of the structure by numerical analysis and selecting the controlled mode. Next, the seismic response reduction effects by multiple TMDs in the shaking table tests and in the reproduced analyses are analyzed, and finally the comparison of the results of both are examined.

2. Design of TMDs

2.1. Analysis models and methods

Fig. 1 and Table 1 show the numerical analysis models used in the preliminary analysis. Table 2 shows the member properties. For the boundary condition, the bases of columns are fixed support. The joints between shell roof and substructure are semi-rigid (rotational spring stiffness: 10kNm/rad) all around. The members are replaced with a circular steel pipes having the same geometrical moment of inertia as the test specimen members on shaking table test. The analysis models use the dimensions of the test specimen drawing shown in the paper (No. C000018: Shake table test of scaled gymnasium frame with cylindrical arch roof – characteristics of seismic response).

Figure 1: Analysis model (●: installation positions of TMDs)

Table 1: Dimensions of arch

Half open angle	θ [deg.]	30
Span	L_x [m]	6
Width	L_y [m]	8
Radius of curvature	R [m]	6
Rise	H [m]	0.704
Height of substructure	H_{s1} [m]	0.9
	H_{s2} [m]	0.725
Total mass of shell structure	M_0 [t]	4.62

Table 2: Member properties

	Slenderness ratio λ	Diameter D [cm]	Thickness t [cm]	Sectional area A [cm ²]	Geometrical moment of inertia I [cm ⁴]
Roof brace	115.8, 118.9	6.84	0.18	4.5	21.09
Roof arch	80.14, 85.89	5.67	0.34	5.73	20.40
Roof beam	91.57	6.62	0.46	8.93	42.60
Beam of longitudinal direction	35.45	16.26	0.31	15.33	488
Column	20.15, 25.01	10.38	0.21	6.55	84.8
Beam of gable direction	135.05	7.39	1.22	23.71	117
Brace of gable direction	56.17	17.90	0.48	26.35	1000

The methods of analyses are a natural vibration analysis considering geometrical non-linearity due to fixed loads and a response spectrum analysis. Eq.(1) is used for the response spectrum analysis.

$${}_k D_j^V = \left| {}_k \beta \cdot {}_k u_j^V \cdot {}_k S_D \right| \quad (1)$$

Where ${}_k D_j^V$ is the maximum vertical response displacement, ${}_k \beta$ is participation factor, ${}_k u_j^V$ is vertical component of eigenvector, ${}_k S_D$ is the value of displacement response spectrum, the subscript k is the order of mode, the subscript j is the node number.

2.2. Selection of controlled mode

The controlled modes are determined by a natural vibration analysis and a response spectrum analysis. In this study, the mode in which ${}_K R_D^V$, the ratio of the maximum vertical response displacement of all nodes calculated by Eq.(2), is greater than 10% is the mode to be controlled by the TMDs (Kumagai et al. [3]).

$${}_K R_D^V = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_j} {}_K D_j^V}{\sum_{k=1}^{N^{em}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} {}_k D_j^V} \quad (2)$$

where K is the order of the controlled mode, N^{em} is the mode order for which the total effective mass ratio reaches 99% and N_j is the number of all nodes in each mode.

Fig. 2 and Table 3 show the free vibration characteristics of each mode. The modes in which ${}_K R_D^V$ is greater than 10% are the 1st and 5th modes, but the 1st mode in which ${}_K R_D^V$ is the largest is the mode to be controlled because it is a single-mode control by TMDs in the experiment. The treated type of TMD is Dual TMDs, taking into account the number of antinodes of controlled mode. The TMDs are installed at X3-Y2 and X3-Y4 nodes which are the antinodes of the 1st mode.

Table 3: Free vibration characteristics of each mode

Modes		1	5	10
Natural period	T_i [sec]	0.262	0.109	0.070
Effective mass ratio	[%]	8.60	13.09	47.29
Vertical equivalent mass	[kg]	1226.4	525.6	218.5
Maximum vertical response displacement ratio	${}_K R_D^V$ [%]	80.9	11.7	5.7
Sum of maximum vertical response displacement ratio	$\sum {}_K R_D^V$ [%]		98.3	

Figure 2: Free vibration characteristics of each mode

2.3. Design of TMDs

Mass ratio, frequency ratio and damping ratio for TMDs are calculated by Eqs. (3)~(5).

$$\mu_N = \frac{m_T}{K M_J} \quad (3) \quad \gamma_N^{(n)} = \frac{\omega_0}{\omega_T^{(n)}} = \frac{T_T^{(n)}}{T_0} \quad (4) \quad \zeta_N^{(n)} = \frac{c_T T_T^{(n)}}{4m_T \pi} \quad (5)$$

where (n) is the order in which the periods of TMDs are long, N is the number of installing TMD, m_T is the mass of one TMD, $K M_J$ is the equivalent mass of K th mode, T_T is the period of TMD, T_0 is the natural period of controlled mode and c_T is the damping factor of TMD.

Frequency ratios and damping ratios are calculated by using the equations for optimal condition formulae (Iwanami and Seto [1], Kamiya et al. [2]). The equations based on the fixed points theory are used for Dual TMD. The designed values by equations for optimal condition formulae are shown in Table 4. The total mass of TMDs in each controlled mode is 6% of the equivalent mass. The TMD of the shorter period is called TMD1 and larger one is called TMD2. The natural period of the TMDs can be adjusted in the range of 91~110% by adjusting the weight and replacing the springs. Since the natural period of the TMDs in the vibration experiment is outside the adjustment range, the shortest period within the adjustment range is used as the natural period of the TMDs. The allowable amplitude of TMDs is ± 30 mm.

Table 4: Designed values by equations for optimal condition formulae

Name of TMD	Mass of TMD m_T [kg]	Natural period of TMD T_T [s]	Mass ratio μ_N	Damping ratio ζ_N	Damping factor c_T [kg/s]	Allowable amplitude [mm]	Equivalent mass M_J [kg]	Natural period of 1st mode T_1 [s]
TMD1	44.8	0.282	0.0365	0.1185	236.6	±30	1226.4	0.262
	36.8	0.232	0.0300	0.1073	214.1			
TMD2	44.8	0.328	0.0365	0.1026	176.2			
	36.8	0.269	0.0300	0.0943	161.9			

3. Performance test of TMDs used in shaking table tests

3.1. Performance tests outline

Fig. 3 shows design drawings of TMD, Photo 1 shows TMDs setup in performance test and Fig. 4 shows location of sensors to be installed in TMD. TMDs have three weight design masses as 36.8, 40.8 and 44.8kg and the natural frequency, vibration mass and damping ratio of TMDs are calculated from total of five free vibration experimental measurements. Damping ratio is calculated using the logarithmic damping ratio shown in Eq.(6) and Fig. 5.

Figure 3: Design drawings of TMD

Photo 1: TMDs setup in performance tests

Figure 4: Location of sensors to be installed in TMD

$$h = \frac{1}{2\pi} \log \left(\frac{X_n}{X_{n+1}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Figure 5: Logarithmic damping ratio

3.2. TMDs performance test results

Fig. 6 shows relationship between single amplitude and damping ratio of TMDs, Fig. 7 shows relationship between single amplitude and natural frequency of TMDs and Table 5 shows the natural frequency, vibration mass and damping ratio when single amplitude is 600cm/s². The damping ratio increases when single amplitude is less than 5mm due to the increase in friction of the bearing as the response amplitude decreases and the vertical movement of the silicon oil in the damper. In the relationship between single amplitude and natural frequency, the amplitude dependence of the natural frequency of TMDs is low. The adopted TMD weight design mass is 36.8kg and the natural frequency and damping ratio are lower than the designed values by equations for optimal condition formulae.

Figure 6: Relationships between single amplitudes and damping ratios

Figure 7: Relationships between single amplitudes and natural

Table 5: TMDs performance test values

Name of TMD	Weight design mass	Natural frequency (period)	Vibration mass	Damping ratio
TMD1	44.8kg	3.82Hz (0.262s)	48.35kg	7.93%
	40.8kg	3.98Hz (0.251s)	44.55kg	8.02%
	36.8kg	4.21Hz (0.238s)	39.74kg	8.60%
TMD2	44.8kg	3.22Hz (0.311s)	50.43kg	8.78%
	40.8kg	3.35Hz (0.299s)	46.64kg	7.77%
	36.8kg	3.55Hz (0.282s)	41.37kg	9.46%

4. Basic information of the test setups installing on roof dual TMDs

The test specimen outline, measurement plan and measurement items are the same as the paper (No. C000018: Shake table test of scaled gymnasium frame with cylindrical arch roof – characteristics of seismic response). Photo 2 shows a general view of the test body installing TMDs and the TMDs installation area. Table 6 shows the loading program. Sweep waves are used to confirm the natural vibration characteristics. The input seismic wave was the observed data of the main shock of the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake wave (April 16) spectrally fitted to the Japanese building code spectrum. In Test Nos. 4-1 to 4-4, the displacement of the TMD weight is fixed, and in Test Nos. 5-1 to 5-4, the weight of the TMD is operated.

(a) General view of the test body installing TMDs

(b) TMDs installation area

Photo 2: General view of the test body and TMDs installation area

Table 6: Loading program

Test No.	Input waves (input frequency or level)	Maximum input acceleration (cm/s ²)	Condition of TMDs
4-1	Sweep wave (0.1~10Hz)	62.8	Fixed
4-2	Seismic wave (50%)	188.0	
4-3	Seismic wave (100%)	400.7	
4-4	Sine wave (4.92Hz)	70.5	
5-1	Sweep wave (0.1~10Hz)	58.6	Operated
5-2	Seismic wave (50%)	184.9	
5-3	Seismic wave (100%)	411.1	
5-4	Sine wave (4.92Hz)	64.9	

5. Seismic response reduction effects by multiple TMDs in the shaking table tests

Fig. 8 shows the Fourier amplitude spectrum of the vertical response acceleration at the X3-Y2 node for 100% seismic input. The response is reduced by about 50% at frequency near the 1st mode while the response increases around 8 Hz due to the fact that the 5th mode is not controlled and to changes in vibration characteristics associated with the operation of the TMDs. Fig. 9 shows the maximum response distribution. In the case of vertical acceleration, the response at the Y4 node is reduced more than that at the Y2 node. In addition, the response reduction effect is the highest (about 40%) for the X3 axis with TMDs. The reduction effect is high at 100% where the seismic motion level is large. The same results as for response acceleration were obtained for vertical displacement. The horizontal acceleration is reduced by approximately 2.50%, although the effect is small. The maximum amplitude of the TMDs at 100% seismic input is about 25mm.

Figure 8: Fourier amplitude spectra (100% seismic input, X3-Y2 node)

Figure 9: Maximum response distributions (seismic wave input, X1 and X3 axes)

6. Reproduced analysis

6.1. Reproduced analysis models and methods

The joints between shell roof and substructure are rigid all around. In order to reproduce the construction errors, the dimensions of arch were changed from the full geometry based on the vertical coordinates of each node surveyed at the time of specimen setup. The member properties are the same as in Fig. 2. The methods of analyses are a natural vibration analysis, a response spectrum analysis and a dynamic elasto-plastic response analysis considering geometrical non-linearity. Rayleigh type is used for damping with

1.67% for the 1st and 2nd modes. 1.67% is the damping factor for the 1st mode in the experiment. The input wave is the vibration in the beam of gable direction measured on the shaking table. Table 7 and Fig. 10 show the free vibration characteristics of the controlled modes. The controlled modes are the 1st and 4th modes in which κR_D^V is greater than 10%. The TMDs to be used are TMD_e model with the performance test values shown in Table 5 and TMD_i model with the optimal condition formulae. For the TMD_i model, two types of models will be considered: the TMD_i1 model, in which the mass ratio of the TMD for the 1st mode is set to the same value as the TMD_e model, and the TMD_i2 model, in which the mass ratio of the TMD for the 1st and 4th modes is set so that the ratio of the total mass $m_T \times N$ of the TMD to the vertical equivalent mass κM_j is 6% for each mode. The TMDs are installed at X3-Y2 and X3-Y4 nodes for both 1st and 4th modes.

Table 7: Free vibration characteristics of controlled modes

Modes		1	4
Natural period	T_0 [sec]	0.204	0.109
Effective mass ratio	[%]	12.55	13.33
Vertical equivalent mass	[kg]	1176	501
Maximum vertical response displacement ratio	κR_D^V [%]	71.1	13.1

Figure 10: Free vibration characteristics of controlled modes

6.2. Seismic response reduction effects by multiple TMDs in the reproduced analysis

Fig. 11 shows the Fourier amplitude spectra of vertical response acceleration at X3-Y2 node during 100% seismic input. During 1st mode control, the reduction effect is higher for installation TMD_i than for installation TMD_e near the 1st mode frequency. Also, during 4th mode control, the response is reduced around 9Hz. Fig. 12 shows the maximum response distribution for X3 axis. For vertical acceleration, the first mode control reduces the response by about 30% regardless of the designed values of the TMDs. In the vertical response, the response reduction is most effective when 1st + 4th mode control is used. On the other hand, the horizontal acceleration response increases depending on the node due to TMDs installation.

	Non-vibration control	TMD_e installation	TMD_i1 installation	TMD_i2 installation		
Controlled modes		1st	1st	1st	4th	1st + 4th

Figure 11: Fourier amplitude spectrum of vertical response acceleration (100% seismic input, X3-Y2 node)

	Non-vibration control	TMD_e installation	TMD_i1 installation	TMD_i2 installation		
Controlled modes		1st	1st	1st	4th	1st + 4th
50% seismic input	○	○	△	▽	▽	▽
100% seismic input	●	●	△	▽	▽	▽

Figure 12: Maximum response distribution (input seismic wave, X3-Y1~Y5 axes)

7. Comparisons of shaking table test and reproduced analysis

Fig. 13 shows the relationship between the response reduction ratio in the shaking table test and the reproduced analysis. As an example, Eq.(7) is the formula for calculating the response acceleration reduction ratio.

$$Re_{A_*}^{shell} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N_I} (A_{*ij}^{shell_c})^2}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N_I} (A_{*ij}^{shell_unc})^2}} \quad (7)$$

where * is the vertical direction V or horizontal direction H , N_j is the number of all nodes for arch roof, N_I is the number of total analysis steps, $shell_c$ is vibration control and $shell_unc$ is non-vibration control. In response displacement, A in equation (7) is replaced with D .

In seismic waves, the response reduction effect in the reproduced analysis is higher than in the shaking table test.

	Table test	TMD_e installation	TMD_i ₂ installation
Controlled modes		1st	1st
50% seismic input	□	○	▽
100% seismic input	■	●	▼

Figure 13: Response reduction ratio in the shaking table test and the reproduced analysis

8. Conclusions

It is concluded as follows, from the above results.

- (1) Design values of multiple TMDs from preliminary analysis in shaking table tests are compared with performance test values from free vibration experiments. In addition, basic information of the test setups installing on roof dual TMDs is given.
- (2) In shaking table tests, the vertical response displacement and acceleration are reduced by up to approximately 40% at X3 axis during seismic wave input.
- (3) In the vertical response in the reproduced analysis, the response reduction effect is highest when the 1st + 4th mode control is used.

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